

ISic1340

I.Sicily inscription 1340

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140837

1. [—?—]CXOYCA [—?—]
2. [—?—]NOCKΩN [—?—]
3. [—?—]EKMEC [—?—]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492948

EDCS 39101713

PHI 140837

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio*

et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV. Berlin.
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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1340. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385816>